

Kinetics of Ion Exchange in Nonaqueous and Mixed Solvents. Part I. Calcium-Hydrogen Exchange in Anhydrous and Aqueous Ethanol

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Kinetics of calcium-hydrogen exchange has been studied in anhydrous and aqueous ethanol solutions. The formal overall rate constant has been found to be of reversible second order. The rates, in general, are slower in perfectly nonaqueous systems and slightly faster in such systems with air-dry resin (water $\approx$ 28%). The rate increases more or less linearly with water in the solvent systems. The rate law has also been studied from the point of view of exchange process as adsorption phenomenon. The rate-determining step is governed equally by the particle and film diffusion steps.

Though the rates and rate laws of ion exchange in nonaqueous media differ considerably from those in aqueous systems, yet the fundamental mechanism of ion exchange has been assumed to be the same in both cases. The rate of ion exchange in systems involving organic solvents is generally slow as compared to the rates in aqueous systems¹⁻⁶. Addition of water to the nonaqueous system increases the rates to a considerable extent^{1-4,6}; hence the behaviour in mixed solvents is somewhat in between the two. Experimental evidence on ion-exchange kinetics with nonaqueous and mixed solvents is still rather scanty. Hence the need is to provide evidences with respect to different organic and mixed solvents using various types of ions.

Attempts have been made in this communication to study the exchange kinetics of calcium ion against hydrogen ion in anhydrous ethanol and ethanol mixed with varying volumes of water. Overall reaction-rate constants have formally been obtained on the basis of reversible exchange reaction. But as such reaction-rate constants have little in common with the rate constants of actual chemical reactions, the exchange under investigation has also been studied as a diffusion phenomenon. The experimental data, hence, have been used to decide the rate-determining step in the above case.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anhydrous calcium chloride was dissolved in anhydrous ethanol to obtain 0.1*M* stock solution. This was used to prepare other nonaqueous (0.05 and 0.025 *M*) and partly aqueous systems containing 5, 10, 20, 40, and 50% water in 0.05 or 0.025 *M* calcium solutions in ethanol.

1. Badamer and Kunin, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1953, 45, 2677.
2. Chance *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 45, 1671.
3. Mattison and Samuelson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1958, 12, 1395.
4. Vermeulen and Huffman, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 45, 1658, 1664.
5. Wilson and Lepidus, *ibid.*, 1956, 48, 692.
6. Shukla and Bhatnagar, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 30, 762.

The kinetics at 30° in nonaqueous and partly aqueous solutions was studied by taking 100 ml of the solution containing calcium ion of a known molarity in a three-necked flask provided with a mechanical glass stirrer in the middle neck. One gram of air-dried Amberlite IR-120(H) (moisture ~ 28%) was always added to the solution and stirring started simultaneously (rate ~ 1000 r.p.m.). The aliquots (5 ml) were withdrawn at suitable intervals by stopping the stirrer for a moment (to avoid resin particles) and acidity generated due to calcium exchange was estimated titrimetrically. Nonaqueous studies were also carried out with dehydrated (vacuum dried) Amberlite IR-120 (H) resin in a similar manner.

TABLE I

Run.	Molarity.	EtOH conc.	$\frac{Ca^{2+}}{H^+}$	$\frac{\bar{C} \bar{D} \delta}{C D \tau_0} (5 + 2 \alpha \frac{Ca^{2+}}{H^+})$.
1	0.050	100%	15.700	0.933
2	0.050	95	18.110	0.936
3	0.050	90	23.100	0.933
4	0.050	80	20.703	0.934
5	0.050	60	22.610	0.935
6	0.050	50	25.320	0.937
7	0.025	100	19.150	0.934
8	0.025	95	9.837	0.930
9	0.025	90	9.393	0.927
10	0.025	80	10.840	0.929
11	0.025	60	10.840	0.927
12	0.025	50	11.130	0.930

DISCUSSION

The experimental data obtained have been used to study the kinetics on the basis of usual assumption that ion exchange is similar to a homogeneous chemical system and also on the basis of the process of interdiffusion of counter ions taking place during ion exchange. Both the approaches have their own merits, though the latter is by far a more suitable one.

Determination of Overall Rate Constant

Considering the exchange of calcium ion against hydrogen form of the resin as a stoichiometric reversible reaction, the process can be represented as

Assuming that the ion exchange under study is a reversible second-order reaction and putting the concentration of calcium ion in variable notations as x = change in concentration at time t , a = initial concentration at $t = 0$, and x_0 = change in concentration

at $t = \infty$ or at equilibrium, the net rate of reaction in the forward direction will be given by

$$-\frac{dx}{dt} = k(a-x)^2 - k'x^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

At equilibrium,

$$\log_{10} \frac{x(a-2x_0) + ax_0}{a(x_0-x)} = k \frac{2a(a-x_0)}{x_0} \times t \quad \dots (3)$$

Since the term $2a(a-x_0)/x_0$ is constant (say k_1), equation (3) assumes the form:

$$\log_{10} \frac{x(a-2x_0) + ax_0}{a(x_0-x)} = k_1 k_2 t \quad \dots (4)$$

If the reversible equation (1) is valid for the exchange reaction under study, then a plot of left hand side term of equation (4) with 't' should provide a straight line or the value of k should be reasonably constant if all terms in equation (3) are calculated on the basis of experimental results.

FIG. 1. Reversible second-order plots at two concentrations with dehydrated resin (plots 1 & 2) and air-dried resin (plots 3 & 4).

made at one concentration under study for different aqueous ethanolic solutions of calcium ion, using air-dry resin. The variation of rate constant with water content of the liquid phase is clear from Fig. 3.

As the plots in Fig. 1 and 2 are linear, the reaction mechanism suggested appears to be satisfactory; hence exchange of calcium against hydrogen ion is reversible second-order reaction. The presence of water in the nonaqueous system does not affect the order. Rates, in general are slower in concentrated solutions in perfectly nonaqueous systems, but these are slightly faster in nonaqueous solvents containing air-dried (28% H₂O) resin sample. Presence of water in nonaqueous solvents increases the rate considerably so as to

In Fig. 1, plots have been made for

$$\log \frac{k(a-2x_0) + ax_0}{a(x_0-x)}$$

against 't' in min. for anhydrous and air-dried resins at 0.05 and 0.025N calcium ion concentrations in anhydrous ethanol. In Fig. 2, similar plots have been

complete the reaction (or attain equilibrium) in about 15 min. at ~ 50% water content of the system. Similar conclusions were drawn by previous workers⁷⁻⁹ for kinetics in non-aqueous or partly aqueous systems.

FIG. 2. Reversible second-order plots for ethanolic solutions containing water.

FIG. 2: (1) 5% water, (2) 10% water, (3) 20% water, (4) 40% water, and (5) 50% water.

FIG. 3. Variation of rate constants with volume of water in nonaqueous solvents.

Consideration of Rate Law on the Basis of Diffusion Phenomenon

The rate-determining step in ion exchange is the interdiffusion of counter ions, as was first recognised by Schulze⁷. But Boyd *et al.*⁸ have shown that when the resin particles are in contact with a well-stirred electrolyte solution, there are two potential rate-determining steps, viz., (1) interdiffusion of counter ions within the ion-exchanger itself (particle diffusion) and (2) interdiffusion of counter ions in the adhering films (film diffusion).

Either of the two or both can be rate-controlling steps in ion exchange. Helfferich⁹ has postulated that if $\bar{C}$ = concentration of fixed ionic groups, C = concentration of solution in equivalents, $\bar{D}$ = interdiffusion coefficient in the ion-exchanger, D = interdiffusion coefficient in the film, r_0 = resin bead radius, δ = film thickness, $\alpha_B^A = \bar{C}_A C_B / \bar{C}_B C_A$ = separation factor where concentrations are expressed on molarity scale, then the value of the term

$$\frac{\bar{C} \bar{D} \delta}{C D r_0} \cdot (5 + 2 \alpha_B^A) \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

7. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 168.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2836.

9. "Ion Exchange", McGraw Hill, New York, Chsp. 6, 1962.

becomes the criterion for the nature of the rate-determining step. If it is $\ll 1$, then it is particle-diffusion controlled and if it is $\gg 1$, then it is film-diffusion controlled. In the intermediate range, i.e. the above term being ≈ 1 , the interdiffusion is about equally fast in the bead and in the film and both the mechanisms affect the rate of ion exchange.

To ascertain the utility of the above expression in deciding the rate-determining step, in any case, one has to justify the conditions under which the expression has been derived. In consideration of the isotopic exchange (and applied to other cases of ion exchange), when particle diffusion is the controlling factor, it has been shown that the fractional attainment of equilibrium $U(t)$ is expressed by the equation:

$$U(t) = 1 - \frac{\bar{Q}_A(t)}{\bar{Q}_A^\circ} = 1 - \frac{6}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} \exp\left(-\frac{\bar{D}t}{r_0^2} \pi^2 n^2\right) \quad \dots (6)$$

where $\bar{Q}_A(t)$ = amount of A in the ion-exchanger at time t , $\bar{Q}_A^\circ$ = initial amount of A in the ion-exchanger; $U(t)$ is defined by

$$U(t) = [\bar{Q}_A^\circ - \bar{Q}_A(t)] / (\bar{Q}_A^\circ - \bar{Q}_A^e)$$

$\bar{Q}_A^e$ = amount of A in exchanger at equilibrium.

The half time of ion exchange is readily calculated from equation (6) by substituting $U(t) = 0.5$ for infinite solution volume condition (vide Helfferich⁹, pp. 260-62).

$$t_{1/2} = 0.030 \frac{r_0^2}{D} \quad \dots (7)$$

In the case of film diffusion as rate-controlling step, the fractional attainment of equilibrium is provided by the expression:

$$U(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{3DCt}{r_0\delta\bar{C}}\right) \quad \dots (8)$$

The half time of ion exchange in this case, as reported by Helfferich⁹ (p. 275), is

$$t_{1/2} = \left(0.167 + 0.004 \frac{A}{B}\right) \frac{r_0\delta\bar{C}}{DC} \quad \dots (9)$$

In the above two cases, the fractional attainment of equilibrium depends on two different dimensionless time parameters, i.e. $\bar{D}t/r_0^2$ in the case of particle diffusion and $DCt/r_0\delta\bar{C}$ in the case of film diffusion.

The curves of U vs. the two time parameters, if plotted together, cut each other at a point corresponding to $t_{1/2}$ or time for $U(t) = 0.5$ in each of the cases. Thus at this hypo-

tical t_1 , the two processes are equal and equations (7) and (9) can be equated and shown to be in the form (5) as

$$\frac{0.030 \cdot r_0^*}{D} = (0.167 + 0.064 \alpha_B^A) \frac{r_0 \delta \bar{C}}{DC}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\bar{D} \delta \bar{C}}{DC r_0} = \frac{0.030}{(0.167 + 0.064 \alpha_B^A)}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(5.56 + 2.1 \alpha_B^A)} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\bar{D} \delta \bar{C}}{DC r_0} (5 + 2 \alpha_B^A) \approx 1 \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

When the particle- and film-diffusion controlled exchanges are equal, the above relation is applicable. This dimensionless modulus becomes smaller than unity when particle diffusion has the longer half life and is larger than unity, whereas film diffusion has longer life. The slower step determines the overall rate. This is why the two values of the left hand side term in equation (5) indicate the nature of the rate-controlling effect.

The separation factor, α_B^A , has been determined experimentally as all values required for its calculation are known from equilibrium data. Putting these values of α_B^A (Table I) in equation (10), the whole term $(\bar{D} \delta \bar{C})/(DC r_0)$ has been evaluated in all cases and the final value for the left-hand side term in equation (5) has been calculated. Table I records such values for the term $(\bar{C} \bar{D} \delta) / CD r_0 (5 + 2 \alpha_B^A)$ which are 0.9 (approx.) in all cases.

Superficially this value may show particle diffusion to be of slightly slower step than the film diffusion. But as the term $(5 + 2 \alpha_B^A)$ in equation (11) is itself an approximation from the more exact term $(5.56 + 2.1 \alpha_B^A)$ shown in an earlier step (eq. 10), this slight deviation of the experimental value of ~ 0.9 from 1.0 has little significance. Therefore it can be finally said that in calcium/hydrogen exchange in ethanolic and partly ethanolic solutions, the interdiffusion is about equally fast in the resin bead and in the film and both mechanisms affect the rate of ion exchange here.

The change in concentration from 0.05 to 0.025 did not change the rate-determining step. Though the presence of a nonaqueous solvent, pure or mixed, caused differences in α_B^A values slightly, yet it did not cause much changes in the value of the dimensionless modulus due to obvious simultaneous changes in $\bar{D}/D$ values.

Of the two mechanisms proposed in the present work, i.e. consideration of ion exchange being similar to a homogeneous chemical system or a diffusion process controlled by particle and/or film diffusion, the authors prefer the exchange in mixed or non-aqueous solvents to be diffusion controlled.

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